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ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE USE OF TESTING TECHNOLOGIES BASED ON A COLLECTIVE APPROACH IN THE PROCESS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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***Abstract.** The article considers general information about compiling test tasks to check residual knowledge in the relevant discipline or to check the final knowledge of the student/trainee based on the discipline program.*

Modern teaching technology considers a test as a tool for measuring the level of knowledge, without which it is impossible not only to identify the quality of the educational standard, but also to optimally manage the educational process. Organization and implementation of regular monitoring of the effectiveness of the educational process in test form involves, first of all, the development of appropriate pedagogical test materials for each discipline for each type of activity of specialists.

In essence, a pedagogical test is a way of formally presenting an intellectual task, which requires the student to perform certain mental actions specially "embedded" in it in the process of solving it.

***Key words.** Pedagogical test, Modern technology, checking, test tasks, formation, education, training, mathematics.*

ВОПРОСЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ТЕСТИРОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ КОЛЛЕКТИВНОГО ПОДХОДА В ПРОЦЕССЕ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ.

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***Аннотация.** Рассматриваются вопросы общие сведения о составлении тестовых заданий для проверки остаточных знаний по соответствующей дисциплине или для проверки итоговых знаний обучающегося/студента на основании программы дисциплины.*

Современная технология обучения рассматривает тест как инструмент измерения уровня знаний, без которого нельзя не только выявить качество исполнения образовательного стандарта, но и оптимально управлять учебным процессом. Организация и проведение регулярного контроля эффективности учебного процесса в тестовой форме предполагает, прежде всего, разработку соответствующих педагогических тестовых материалов для каждой дисциплины по каждому виду деятельности специалистов.

По сути педагогический тест – это способ формального представления интеллектуальной задачи, предусматривающий выполнение учащимся в процессе ее решения определенных умственных действий, специально в нем «заложенных».

Ключевые слова. *Педагогический тест, Современная технология, проверка, тестовых заданий, формирования, образования, обучения, математика.*

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONIDA KOLOBATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TEST TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

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“Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar, pedagogika va psixologiya” kafedrasida o‘qituvchisi

Annotatsiya. Maqolada tegishli fan bo'yicha qoldiq bilimlarni tekshirish yoki fan dasturi asosida talaba/stajorning yakuniy bilimni tekshirish uchun test topshiriqlarini tuzish haqida umumiy ma'lumotlar ko'rib chiqiladi.

Zamonaviy o'qitish texnologiyasi testni bilim darajasini o'lchash vositasi sifatida ko'rib chiqadi, bu holda nafaqat ta'lim standarti sifatini aniqlash, balki o'quv jarayonini optimal boshqarish ham mumkin emas. Ta'lim jarayoni samaradorligini test shaklida muntazam monitoringini tashkil etish va amalga oshirish, eng avvalo, mutaxassislar faoliyatining har bir turi bo'yicha har bir fan bo'yicha tegishli pedagogik test materiallarini ishlab chiqishni nazarda tutadi.

Aslida, pedagogik test intellektual vazifani rasmiy ravishda taqdim etish usuli bo'lib, uni hal qilish jarayonida o'quvchidan unga maxsus "o'rnatilgan" ma'lum aqliy harakatlarni bajarishni talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. *Pedagogik test, Zamonaviy texnologiya, tekshirish, test topshiriqlari, shakllantirish, ta'lim, tarbiya, matematika.*

in accordance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan " [On Education](#) " and " [On the National Program for Personnel Training](#) ", as well as the [Resolution](#) of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 No. PP-2909 "On measures for the further development of the higher education system", in order to admit gifted students to educational institutions of the republic through testing, the Cabinet of Ministers decrees:

1. To define the main tasks of the State Testing Center under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the State Testing Center):

implementation of state policy in the field of test selection for admission to educational institutions of the republic;

ensuring the objectivity, reliability and fairness of testing results;

formation of a test task database, improvement of pedagogical measurement tools;

organization and conduct of test trials, coordination of this process, publication of test materials, analysis of test trial results;

development of a national system for assessing the level of proficiency in foreign languages.

2. To assign responsibility to the director of the State Testing Center for ensuring the high-quality conduct of entrance tests to educational institutions.

3. To approve the Regulation on the State Testing Center under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its structure in accordance with [Appendices No. 1 , 2](#) .

Establish the total maximum number of management personnel of the State Testing Center under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan at 72 units.[1].

Grant the director of the State Testing Center under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan the right to make, if necessary, changes to the structure of the Center within the established total number in agreement with the relevant

information and analytical department of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

4. Determine the sources of funding for the activities of the State Testing Center:
funds of the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
funds of sponsors - individuals and legal entities, residents and non-residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
other sources not prohibited by law.[1].

The quality of education of graduates of an educational institution is ensured by a system of methods for organizing and managing the educational process. Constantly incoming objective information about the progress of students provides the necessary data to adjust the methods of managing educational activities and improve their effectiveness. Therefore, the organization of objective control of students' knowledge is an integral part of the organization of the educational process.

Testing in mathematics plays a key role in assessing students' knowledge and is an integral part of the educational process. A mathematics test allows not only to check the assimilation of educational material, but also to identify gaps in knowledge, which is especially important for preparing for exams. With the help of tests, teachers can adapt the curriculum, focusing on students' weaknesses. In addition, independent completion of the online mathematics test allows students to independently assess their level and prepare for upcoming exams [2].

The educational environment of the university is one of the structural components of the educational environment. Its generalized component-element composition can be presented as follows:

- content component (main and additional professional and educational programs implemented in the university, adopted concepts of training, education, formation and development of personality, organizational and methodological documents regulating the activities, communication and behavior of employees and students);
- educational component (forms, methods, ways of activity (interaction), style of communication and behavior);

- technical component (computer equipment and its software; automated knowledge control system);
- virtual component (remote support);
- social component (space of interpersonal interaction between students, teachers, psychologists, administration and types of this interaction);
- organizational component (infrastructure of the university);
- subject component (elements of the educational and scientific material base, living and hygienic conditions).

1. The considered structure of the environment is approximate. The specific list of components of the environment and the content of its elements are determined by the profile and specific features of each university. However, regardless of the content and other differences, the educational environment of the university is also an open self-developing system built on synergetic principles:

2. the principle of evolutionary movement, according to which the natural order of education is not the only possible one;

3. the principle of harmonization, according to which the formal mathematical language cannot be considered as universal without interaction with conceptual, spiritual, humanitarian methods, i.e. humanization and humanitarization should become fundamental in modern higher education;

4. the principle of variability: education and training of a highly qualified specialist is carried out on a multi-variant and alternative basis; the presence of moments of instability associated with the choice of a further educational trajectory; a conflict of styles in the learning process leads to the need to change the educational trajectory;

5. the principle of comparative analysis of the value system: the development of the student's personality is realized on the basis of comparing his own system of personal meanings (values) with what has been accumulated in the culture;

6. the principle of multiplicity in the operation of choosing values and further development paths that accompanies the educational process; the choice, as a rule, is determined by the semantic significance for the student of the studied realities; the

process of training a specialist includes a variety of trends, accompanied by spontaneous and controlled processes of destruction of old and emergence of new systems, search for and acquisition of new meanings;

7. the principle of non-linear interaction: education can be considered innovative if it is a process of non-linear interaction of a person with an intellectual environment, in which the person perceives it to enrich his own inner world and, thanks to this, matures to multiply the potential of the environment itself;

8. the principle of openness: the educational environment should be an open system (consist of subsystems between which there is a constant exchange of information; be a subsystem of a higher-order system and exchange information with its other subsystems);

9. the principle of self-development: the educational environment should ensure the transition from management to self-management, from development under the influence of external factors to self-development under the influence of internal factors [9].

According to V. M. Kureichik and V. I. Pisarenko, the educational environment of higher education allows one to learn the rules of self-organization of oneself and social systems, but only if pedagogical interaction is aimed at developing the student's personality, determining the meaning and motives for learning not only for future professional activity, but also at developing and activating the personal structures of consciousness: criticality, motivation, reflection, collision, mediation, autonomy, etc., in other words, at self-actualization of the student's personality. Focus on the process of self-organization of the individual by means of their internal resources, requiring external initiative [9].

The internal structure of the educational environment of the university is not static, it is constantly updated and modified under the influence of external factors (environments), the components interact and mutually influence each other, as a result of the interaction of which with the individual, the formation of personality occurs. It is important to note that the system-forming element of this model is pedagogical

interaction in the process of productive activity of the participants in the educational process. The more the student influences the goals, content and course of his education in the educational environment, the greater the influence it has on him. The educational environment of the university appears as a self-organizing and self-developing system due to the flexible and non-deterministic hierarchy of structural elements, implying information and energy openness and activity of the system components due to constant interaction with another system or the external environment. Self-organization of the educational environment of the university acts as a process or a set of processes that contribute to maintaining its optimal functioning, promoting self-completion, self-restoration and self-change of this systemic formation, for example, the emergence of new methods or techniques of teaching.

The closest to the modern understanding is the definition of a digital educational resource as a product created to solve specific educational problems and characterized by completeness (to solve the set problems, no additional external resources are required); interactivity (users can make changes, adapt the resource to their needs); multimedia (content is presented in various formats: text, audio, video, etc.) or can be delivered through different channels (audio, video, text, etc.) [7, p. 10]. There are multiple classifications of digital educational resources; in the context of our study, we will highlight the following types of resources focused on distance and e-learning:

- information educational resources (resources on digital media, resources of the Web 1.0 and Web 2.0 categories);
- electronic courses based on the Learning Management System and Moodle (elearning.unn.ru. - the online course system of UNN, etc.); -massive open online courses (MOOC) (mooc.unn.ru – open online courses of Lobachevsky University, etc.).

Digital equipment for educational purposes, including mobile devices, digital laboratories, VR&AR technologies, interactive teaching aids, small information technology tools.

Digital educational tools are software products for organizing the educational process, for example:

- network interaction tools (Zoom, Skype, Microsoft Teams, Google Hangouts, Cisco Webex Meetings, etc.)
- editors (text, graphic, video, etc.);
- mobile applications;
- dynamic graphic environments and packages (GeoGebra, Mathcad, etc.);
- virtual boards (AMW board, MIRO, Whiteboard Fox, Scribblar, etc.);
- infographics.

The system components complement and enrich each other, providing a qualitatively new education in the context of digitalization.

When organizing the process of teaching mathematics in a rich digital educational environment, it is also necessary to take into account the risks of using the digital environment.

Therefore, it is necessary to use modern information technologies in the process of teaching mathematics in a balanced way to complement and expand the search and research activities of students. Mathematical education, as a structural component of the educational environment of the university, also affects its self-organization and self-development. We believe that the process of teaching mathematics in an open self-developing environment of the university is presented through the integration of interactive teaching methods and information and communication technologies to enrich pedagogical interaction and move it to a qualitatively new level, with a high degree of interactivity, in order to achieve personal-value and professionally significant goals of teaching mathematics. Mathematical research methods mediated by information technologies, innovative models of teaching mathematics, interactive forms of teaching mathematics, pedagogical interaction enrich the educational environment of the University:

- competency-based approach to learning, based on the generalized ability of subjects of the educational process to universal practical activities;

-criteria for the functioning of the educational environment are the qualities of the student's personality, formed in this environment;

-self-organization of the environment, conditioned by both the expansion of educational resources of the environment and the construction of various connections between various environments (components), resources and participants;

-collective cooperation and co-creation with the involvement of various social, professional and scientific communities;

-active use of global network technologies, among which priority are Internet technologies and services that provide access to environmental resources from any device (computer, tablet, cell phone);

-availability of various environmental resources, determined by the ability to access them at any time from any geographic point;

-organization of network educational programs with other universities (Russian and foreign).

-focus on the student's personality, on self-actualization as a goal;

-the most favorable conditions for personal self-development;

-self-education, self-training and self-development as the leading forms of education at the university;

-flexible individualized nature of education;

-rich professionally-oriented content;

Let's define the elements of the interactive process of teaching mathematics for the design and functioning of an open self-developing educational environment of the university:

1) the process of teaching mathematics is the subject of educational activity, in which the student is placed in the position of the subject of the activity;

2) the leading goal of teaching mathematics at the university is the personal and professional growth of students through self-actualization of the individual;

3) pedagogical interaction in the process of teaching mathematics is organized through the integration of interactive learning and information technology;

- 4) an interactive model of acquiring knowledge by students through active "extraction" and generation of new personal knowledge;
- 5) development of the internal motivation of the student;
- 6) organizational forms of training, along with traditional ones, are supplemented by open educational courses and resources of various authors and groups of authors;
- 7) the basic technological means of teaching mathematics are network technologies, including web 2.0 technologies, cloud technologies, distance technologies, etc.;
- 8) interactive methods of teaching mathematics as leading and priority methods of teaching at the university;
- 9) the focus of the teacher's activities is shifting towards designing, creating and maintaining open educational courses, developing schedules for their completion, acting as a consultant on various learning paths;
- 10) the priority means of interaction between teachers and students are social Internet services.

Thus, mathematical education should be carried out in a digital educational environment, filled with new educational tools and qualitatively modify the educational process.

The content of the test task should be aimed at obtaining an unambiguous conclusion from the test taker:

1. When creating tests to check residual knowledge in the relevant discipline or to check the final knowledge of the student, the content area of the test and the testing objectives are determined based on the discipline program.
2. The content of the test should correspond to the content of the academic discipline. Test tasks should cover all important aspects of the content area in the correct proportion.
3. It is necessary to include in the tests only the most important, basic knowledge expressing the essence, content, laws and patterns of the phenomena under consideration. All controversial points of view permissible in a scientific dispute should be excluded from the test tasks.

4. Each educational element should have a certain average measure of difficulty, which must be taken into account in the process of knowledge control.

5. When developing a plan of test assignments for a discipline, an approximate breakdown of the percentage content of sections is made and the required number of assignments (but not less than 3) is determined for each section of the discipline (for each didactic unit) based on its importance and the number of hours allocated for its study in the program.

6. General recommendations for test assignments.

. The main terms of the test task must be clearly and explicitly defined. Test tasks must be pragmatically correct and designed to assess the level of students' academic achievement in a specific area of knowledge. Test tasks must be formulated in the form of condensed short judgments.

In the content of the test task, the defining feature must be necessary and sufficient.

Test tasks that require the test taker to make detailed conclusions on the requirements of the test tasks should be avoided.

When constructing test situations, various forms of their presentation can be used, as well as graphic and multimedia components for the purpose of rationally presenting the content of the educational material.

The number of words in a test task should not exceed 10-12, if this does not distort the conceptual structure of the test situation. The main thing is a clear and explicit reflection of the content of a fragment of the subject area.

The average time for a test task should not exceed 1.5 minutes.

7. It is recommended to comply with the following test parameters:

It is necessary to select tasks that comprehensively reflect the main topics of the academic discipline. Test assignments for a specific academic discipline should most fully reflect its content and key concepts in order to have a high-quality objective assessment of students' knowledge. Including secondary content elements in the test

may lead to unjustified conclusions about knowledge or ignorance of the academic discipline.

It is necessary to maintain proportions in the number of test tasks on the topics of the academic discipline.

It is necessary to check the correspondence of the content of test tasks to the knowledge, skills and abilities assessed in students.

Each test task must be definite, logical, without incorrect wording, highlighting one subject of measurement (key concept, term, rule, definition, etc.).

8. Recommendations for wording test tasks.

The main elements of a test task are the instruction, the task (content part), and the answers to the task.

The instruction to the test tasks determines the list of actions when passing the test. It must be adequate to the form and content of the task ("indicate the correct answer (answers)", "establish a match", "determine the correct sequence", "enter the correct answer").

The terminology used should not go beyond the basic textbooks and regulatory documents. The substantive part of the task should not include elements of instructions. The substantive part of the task is formulated in the logical form of a statement, and not in the form of a question; it should not contain ambiguous and unclear formulations, introductory phrases, double negation, value judgments that clarify the subjective opinion of the subject. All repeated words should be excluded from the answers and moved to the substantive part of the task.[5].

In the substantive part and in the answers, it is necessary to exclude the words "big, small, many, few, less, more, often, always, rarely, never ...". All answer options must be competently coordinated with the substantive part of the task, uniform in content and structure, equally attractive. Clear differences are required between the answers. The correct answer is unambiguous and should not rely on hints.

Among the answers, there should be no answers that follow from one another. The answer options must not include the formulations "all of the above", "all statements

are true", "the listed answers are not true", since such answers violate the logical structure of the test task or contain a hint. The number of test tasks with negation must be minimal. In this case, the particle "not" is highlighted in bold[1].

Multiple Choice Tasks. This is the main type of task used in achievement tests. Multiple choice tasks imply the presence of variability in the choice. The test taker must choose one of the proposed options, among which most often only one is correct.

Recommendations for tasks with multiple answers

1. Any ambiguity or vagueness of wording must be eliminated in the text of the task;
2. The main part of the task is formulated very briefly, no more than one sentence of seven to eight words;
3. The task must have an extremely simple syntactic structure;
4. The main part of the task includes as many words as possible, leaving 2-3 key words for the answer for a given problem;
5. All answers to one task must be approximately the same length, or in some tasks the correct answer may be shorter than others;
6. All associations that facilitate the selection of the correct answer by guesswork must be excluded from the text;
7. The frequency of choosing the same place number for the correct answer in different tasks should be approximately the same;
8. All repeating words are excluded from the answers by entering them in the main text of the tasks;
9. It is not recommended to use the words "all", "none", "never", "always", "none of the listed", "all of the listed" in the answers, since in some cases they contribute to guessing the correct answer;
10. Answers that follow from one another should be excluded from the number of incorrect ones;
11. Tasks containing evaluative judgments or opinions of the subject on any issue should be excluded from the number of test questions;

12. All answer options should be equally attractive to the subjects;

13. None of the answer options should be partially correct, turning into correct under certain additional conditions;

1. The main part of the task is formulated as a statement that turns into a true or false statement after substituting the answers;

2. The answer to one task should not serve as a key to the correct answers to other test tasks, i.e. distractors from one task should not be used as answers to other test tasks (a distractor is an incorrect but plausible answer in test tasks with a choice of one or several correct answers);

3. All answers should be parallel in structure and grammatically consistent with the main part of the test task.

4. Closed-form test tasks should contain 3–6 answer options for each question, including at least one correct and at least one incorrect.

5. Instructions for multiple-choice tasks: Select the letter(s) corresponding to the option(s) of the correct answer(s).

Advantages of closed-type tasks:

Tasks can be reliable, since there are no factors associated with subjective assessments that reduce reliability. The assessment of tasks is completely objective: there can be no differences between the assessments of different examiners. The ability of the examinees to formulate answers well is not taken into account.

Tasks of this type are easy to process, testing is carried out quickly.

A simple filling algorithm reduces the number of random errors and typos.

These tasks allow you to cover large areas of knowledge, which is especially important for achievement tests.

Machine processing of answers is possible.

Low probability of guessing the correct answers.

It is possible to obtain an accurate assessment of the content of the test, which is especially important for determining the test's compliance with the research objectives

Open-ended tasks. Requires a conclusion formulated by the test subject on the requirements of the task. It has the form of an incomplete statement in which one or more key elements are missing. Key elements can be: a number, a word or a phrase. When formulating a task, a dash or ellipsis must be put in place of the key element. The missing element (correct conclusion) in an open-ended task is entered by the test subject in place of the dash and/or in a special field clearly visible to the test subject.[12].

These include two types of tasks: - additions (tasks with limited answers). In these tasks, subjects also independently answer questions, but their capabilities are limited.

Limitations ensure the objectivity of the assessment of the result of the task, and the wording of the answer should allow for an unambiguous assessment. Thus, the Informatization of education has created the basis for the transition of the educational process to a new level, its main task is to train specialists who are guaranteed to be in demand in the labor market, easily and freely master digital technologies, as well as ensuring continuous training and advanced training through e-learning. Digital technologies in the modern world are not only a tool, but also an environment of existence that opens up new opportunities: training at any convenient time, continuous education, the ability to design individual educational routes, from consumers of electronic resources to become creators.

Advantages of online tests in mathematics: Firstly, they are available at any time of the day, which allows you to flexibly plan your studies. Secondly, such tests are usually compiled taking into account current educational standards, which will help you to keep up to date with the latest changes in the program. Finally, the use of online tests helps to develop skills in working with information in digital format, which is important in the modern world. The educational function of pedagogical tests is to organize educational activities, while the student receives timely information about his achievements in studies, is informed about the mistakes made and eliminates them in order to begin studying new material. The implementation of the educational function of control requires the teacher to know the characteristics of the students in the class,

their achievements in mastering the educational material for a specific period of study time, i.e. the teacher must have complete information about the dynamics of the educational process.[11].

The educational function of pedagogical control concerns the development of students' learning motivation, the formation of responsibility for the results of their activities, the formation of diligence and perseverance, the ability to self-education, and the development of communication skills. Pedagogy includes a significant conceptual and terminological apparatus from a scientific point of view. However, the concepts in pedagogy have different interpretations among authors, and the term pedagogical diagnostics is no exception. Having analyzed a number of works, we came to the conclusion that the interpretation of the concept of "pedagogical diagnostics" directly depends on the author's view on the assessment of the results of pedagogical activity, due to its complexity and multifaceted nature.

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